

Management of Secondary School Curriculum for Adequate Foundation on Students Transiting to Tertiary Institutions in Dutsinma, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examined the management of secondary school curriculum for adequate foundation on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma, Katsina State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of 300 respondents, (50 principals, 150 teachers and 100 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma). The sample size of the study consists of 150, (25 principals, 50 teachers and 75 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma), selected from target population using stratified random sampling techniques. A self-structured Four-Likert questionnaire of 20 items was used to collect the data. The instrument was validated by two experts from Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation, Federal University Dutsinma. The reliability index was 0.67. Frequency and percentages were used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study reveal that adequate strategies were used for teaching. It also reveals that several factors like inadequate teaching facilities and shortage of teachers in some special subject areas were some of factors militating against effective implementation of the curriculum. The study therefore concludes that the management should continue to use the appropriate teaching methods and see how the factors militating against the provision of pragmatic approach in addressing inadequate implementation of the secondary school curriculum could be addressed. The study recommends amongst others that the government should employ, train and retrain teachers and also provide the necessary facilities for easy teaching and learning in schools.

Keyword: Management, curriculum, transiting, adequate foundation.

Introduction

This study examined the management of secondary school curriculum for adequate foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Local Government Area of Katsina State, Nigeria. Curriculum is a standard-based sequence of planned experiences where students practice and achieve proficiency in content and applied learning skills. Curriculum is the central guide for all educators as to what is essential for teaching and learning, so that every student has access to rigorous academic experiences. The structure, organization, and considerations in a curriculum are created in order to enhance student learning and facilitate instruction. Curriculum must include the necessary goals, methods, materials and assessments to effectively support instruction and learning. This all-important assignment is implemented by the management and teachers of the school. The researcher therefore anchors his study on the explanation of planning and management during curriculum planning and program implementation, resources necessary, curriculum reform and innovations, counseling and guidance and education to enhance the necessary foundation laying for the students transiting to tertiary institution.

This study examines the role of various stakeholders in the school environment. Curriculum implementation in schools through policy formulation, through planned activities is the core and essential element that creates school business upon which schools' stakeholders interact for the purpose of achieving a common goal of educating the people of any society. There is need to catch up with the changing needs of institutions as well as coping with meeting the challenges of individual reforms that looks a daunting task, all of them to be achieved within a limited time frame presents a management challenge that thus requires planning. This is managed through detailed strategy. To create this strategy, the management team has to analyze the current

situation by doing a thorough environmental scan and by identifying the gap between the current state and the desired program. To be implemented, the vision of the new program needs to rely on the generation of several potential avenues to come up with optimal solutions, likely involving some form of innovation. Indeed, to come up with the most promising ideas, there needs to be an environment conducive to reflection and experimentation. Throughout the phases of analysis, decision making and implementation, specific activities need to be organized to engage college members. Furthermore, such a profoundly impacting project needs to include a parallel change management strategy to account for expected human resistance, both individual and collective (internal culture). This article proposes a method and several concrete actions to help leaders and managers support the development and implementation of a new and innovative curriculum to promote and support advancement of local professional practice.

Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014), posit that organizing a curriculum that would create and lay adequate foundation for students transiting to tertiary institutions, as to meet up with the challenges of the new environment is a very huge challenge. Koster, Schalekamp and Meijerman (2017) stated that the success of foundation laying on students is influenced by several factors, including the current state of the curriculum, the local culture and support from higher management. The main reason why management of curriculum is more challenging is that it involves all personnel working within a college. Moreover, the further the project moves away from known and predictable habits and customs (culture), the more it will bring resistance due to fear, uncertainty, perceived lack of competence and time requirements, amongst others (Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014). They continued by stating that laying of foundation on students through curriculum implementation is a human challenge in addition to a technical one and needs to be managed as such. It is a matter of the heart and mind. Failure to address the human aspect and local culture can create a situation where the project cannot be completed as intended. Indeed, there is a saying by Peter Drucker that “culture eats strategy for breakfast”.

Blanchard, Zigarmi, and Zigarmi (2013) posited that because curricular implementation takes such a long-term project, measured by the time it takes to create an impact, plus the time to graduate students moving to tertiary institutions, it should prepare them for current but mainly future challenges, based on insight, experience and a good understanding of where the students are going. In addition, it should incorporate as much pedagogical innovation as possible to make it relevant to the students’ needs and to last for a significant number of years. Going through this lengthy process would suggest more radical changes, a real transformation, rather than tinkering with knowledge and skills by an incremental change (Noble, Shaw, Coombes and O’Brien 2011).

Curricular is a significant tool in realizing the goals of education, and its realization needs a structured long-term direction; it needs a strategy. Bolman and Deal, in Schein and Schein (2017) stated that “a vision without a strategy remains an illusion.” The strategy is the separation between thinking and doing things (Mintzberg, 2020). De Langen (2012) went further to state that it is about choosing a path that is coherent with the vision and with the prevailing culture. Forming a strategy is a process that requires 3 major phases (Johnson 2017). First, one needs to scan the environment, to analyze and diagnose the current situation and the current strategic position, and to identify the drivers for change to develop the vision. Second, one must think of different solutions that have to be compared and contrasted to make the strategic and innovative choices supporting the vision, allowing the gap between the current and the desired state to be bridged. Third, the solutions need to be implemented so that the strategy is converted into action and the curriculum evolves towards the new vision.

According to the well-known Kübler–Ross theory (1969) stated that members of a secondary school will go through a series of emotions during the project, as their level of competence is challenged and they are taken outside their comfort zone. From the current situation, they will start by being in shock, then by expressing denial and frustration and by being depressed. Finally they will experiment, accept, engage in and committed to the new situation. On a long-term project such as curricular implementation, there will be a lot of time spent managing negative emotions until the general feeling returns to a more positive attitude. Constant and consistent communication and reassurance are key during the process. Thus, in parallel to the strategy related to curriculum implementation itself, a second strategy needs to be focused on managing change. This is necessary to give a chance to the project to succeed. Indeed, resistance to change is a normal phenomenon in any project that brings about any form of innovation (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2018). Resistant individuals can use any weakness to derail such a demanding project.

The inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum has been discovered to have so much negative implications on students who are transiting into the various tertiary institutions. These included, failure in examinations, inability to adjust to the new environment, low CGPA in school, lack of appropriate study habits (Alade, 2013), and so on. This means that the curriculum implementation strategy has to be convincing, to be based on needs and to propose evidence-based solutions so that it is as robust as possible and cannot be easily dismissed. Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) stated that in addition, there is the need to be a genuine concern and specific activities to manage change, tailored to the local context and

the prevailing societal culture, as some societies are more eager to experiment and others are more conservative. There are a number of changes in management frameworks that can help to prepare for this reality Kotter and Schlesinger (2008) and Hayes (2014). Throughout this article, change management activities that will support the three main steps of forming and implementing the main strategy will be presented. They are mainly based on the 8-step model of change management proposed by (Kotter 1969).

Parallel processes of (1) the curriculum implementation strategy, (2) the change management strategy (Kotter 1969) and (3) the curriculum development steps. Moreau, Al-Taweel, Qaddoumi, and Alowayesh, (2019) further stated that Curriculum development steps can vary, but those described are based on previous experience. Although depicted as linear, from top to bottom, the processes allow for some iterations when downstream steps uncover flaws in upstream assumptions or decisions or when new information becomes available. Communication is important throughout the curriculum implementation. Implementation support team. Embedded in the curriculum and change in management strategies are a series of curriculum development steps that one can follow to obtain the desired goal. This can take many shapes and forms, and it is not the main focus of this article. To illustrate management of a curriculum implementation in a way that is not too abstract, the curricular development steps that have been previously reported would be used (Moreau, Al-Taweel, Qaddoumi, and Alowayesh, 2019). Thus, this article presents the management of an innovative curriculum reform from the higher perspective of strategy formation that includes an embedded change management strategy allowing curriculum development and implementation according to logical steps of curriculum development to enhance solid foundation for students heading to the various tertiary institutions of learning.

Most newly admitted students into the different tertiary institutions find it very difficult to adjust, especially in academic programmes which they enlisted. This is because of the level of foundation acquired in both primary and post-primary institutions. The level of investigations carried out by many scholars have indicated this fact. So many schools do not include reading culture as part of the curriculum. To this effect, so many students do not have the culture of reading on their own which would have increased their understanding horizon as they get into tertiary institutions of their choice. Teaching pedagogy in implementation of the curriculum has also contributed to the poor foundation laying of the students. Choice of programme which the students have little or no background contribute so much to negative performance of students. The study therefore examines the management of secondary school curriculum implementation for adequate foundation on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma LGA, Katsina State.

Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to examine the management of secondary school's curriculum implementation for adequate foundation on students transiting to the tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area of Katsina State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the management strategies/pedagogy used in curriculum implementation for adequate foundation of students transiting to tertiary institutions Dutsinma Local Government Area.
2. Examine the factors militating against adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area.
3. Examine the impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on the foundation on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Dutsinma Local Government Area.

Research Questions

Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. They are:

1. What are the strategies/pedagogy used by the management in implementing secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Local Government Area?
2. What are the factors militating against the adequate implementing secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma LGA Local Government Area?
3. What are the perceived impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Methodology

This study adopted survey research design. Survey research design was appropriate because it sought to dealing and gathering of information from respondents. The population of the study consists of 300 respondents, (50 principals, 150 teachers and 100 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma). The sample size of the study consists of 150, (25 principals, 50

teachers and 75 second year students of Federal University Dutsinma), selected from target population using stratified random sampling techniques. A self-structured Four-Likert questionnaire of 20 items on Management of Secondary School Curriculum Implementation for Adequate Foundation Laying on Students transiting to the Tertiary Institutions (MSSCIAFLSTI) in Dutsinma LGA, was developed and used for data collection for the study. The instrument was validated by two experts from Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation, Federal University Dutsinma. The instrument was assessed to ensure its clarity and the appropriateness of the items. The reliability index was 0.67 using test re-test reliability test. Frequency and percentages were used to answer the research questions. There were two sections of the instrument. Section A consists of the demographic information on the respondents, while section B sought for information on strategies/pedagogy used by school management, factors militating against adequate curriculum implementation and perceived impact of inadequate implementation of the curriculum. This section is also divided into three clusters to take care of the three research questions. The research questions were analyzed frequencies and percentage, while the hypotheses were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are the strategies/pedagogy used by the management in implementing secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Table 1: Indicates the frequency and percentage of responses of the respondents on the strategies/pedagogy used by the management for adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum in Dutsinma LGA.

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Decision
1.	The curriculum content has the adequate information for teaching and learning	150	120	80.0 %	Accepted
2.	There are adequate and competent teachers	150	145	97.0 %	Accepted
3.	Teaching was not made teacher-centered	150	149	99.3 %	Accepted
4.	Teachers use the facilities in teaching	150	135	90.0 %	Accepted
5.	Teachers are acquainted with the modern methods of teaching	150	146	97.3 %	Accepted
6.	The syllabus and the scheme of work are always covered adequately	150	135	90.0 %	Accepted

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of responses of the respondents on the strategies/pedagogy used by the management for adequate implementations of secondary school curriculum. From the table, it was observed that the items on the table were alluded to by the respondents, indicating that the management was using the appropriate strategies/pedagogy for the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum to lay solid foundation for the transiting students to tertiary institutions. In line with the above assertion, Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014), posited that organizing a curriculum that would create and lay adequate foundation for students transiting to tertiary institutions, as to meet up with the challenges of the new environment is a very huge challenge. Noble, Shaw, Coombes and O'Brien (2011) in addition stated that curriculum implementation should incorporate as much pedagogical innovation as possible to make it relevant to the students' needs and to last for a significant number of years. Going through this lengthy process would suggest more radical changes, a real transformation, rather than tinkering with knowledge and skills by an incremental change.

Research Question Two: What are the factors militating against the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Table 2: Shows the respondents' responses on the factors militating against adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for the foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma LGA.

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Decision
1.	Inadequate qualified teachers to handle the curriculum appropriately	150	105	70.0	Accepted
2.	Lack of teaching aids as indicated in the curriculum for smooth teaching and learning.	150	115	77.0	Accepted

3.	Inadequate laboratories and their facilities	150	123	82.0	Accepted
4.	Inadequate library and its facilities	150	125	83.3	Accepted
5.	Teachers' method of teaching	150	68	45.3	Not Accepted
6.	Students' study habits	150	139	93.0	Accepted

From table 2 above, it was observed that the respondents asserted to the fact that several factors militate against adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for the foundation laying of students transiting to tertiary institutions, except item 5 that disagreed to this allusion. In line with this agreement, Koster, Schalekamp and Meijerman (2017) stated that the success of foundation laying on students is influenced by several factors, including the current state of the curriculum, the local culture and support from higher management. The main reason why management of curriculum is more challenging is that it involves all personnel working within a college.

Research Question Three: What are the perceived impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area?

Table Three: Shows the responses of the respondents on the perceived impact of the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum for the foundation laying on students transiting to tertiary institution in Dutsinma LGA?

S/N	Statement	No. of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Decision
1.	Leads to failure in SSCE WAEC and NECO examinations	150	128	85.3	Accepted
2.	Leads to examination malpractice	150	146	97.3	Accepted
3.	Takes time for students to adjust in tertiary institutions	150	131	87.3	Accepted
4.	Inability to understand the system as new students to a new environment	150	127	85.0	Accepted
5.	May lack the appropriate study habit	150	93	62.0	Accepted
6.	May lead to joining bad peers	150	89	59.3	Accepted
7.	Students may be scoring low CGPA	150	138	92.0	Accepted
8.	Could lead to final withdrawal or dropout from school	150	127	85.0	Accepted

Table 3 shows responses of the respondents on the perceived impact of inadequate implementation of the secondary school curriculum on students transiting to tertiary institution. The respondent asserted to the fact that those students who are inadequately prepared face so much challenges in tertiary institutions of their choice. In line with the above, Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) stated that there is the need to be a genuine concern and specific activities to manage change, tailored to the local context and the prevailing societal culture, as some societies are more eager to experiment and others are more conservative. There are a number of change in management frameworks that can help to prepare for this reality to avert inadequacies in school in implementation of the school curriculum. Kotter and Schlesinger (2008) and Hayes (2014).

Discussion of findings

The research question one sought to examine the strategies/pedagogies used in managing the implementation of secondary school curriculum on the students transiting tertiary institutions. From the frequency and percentage table, it was observed that the items on the table were alluded to by the respondents, indicating that the management was using the correct strategies/pedagogy for the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum to lay solid foundation for the transiting students to tertiary institutions. Keesing-Style, Nash, and Ayres (2014), supported this findings by positing that organizing a curriculum that would create and lay adequate foundation for students transiting to tertiary institutions, as to meet up with the challenges of the new environment is a very huge challenge.

The major findings of research question two asserted that so many factors militate against inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on students transiting to the tertiary institutions. It was found that these factors which included inadequate qualified teachers, inadequate laboratory and its facilities, libraries, reading culture, etc., have created so much barriers on the students transiting to tertiary institutions. Koster, Schalekamp and Meijerman (2017) stated that the success of foundation laying on students is influenced by several factors, including the current state of the curriculum, the local culture

and support from higher management. The main reason why management of curriculum is more challenging is that it involves all personnel working within a college.

The findings on research question three revealed that, there are so many perceived impact due to the inadequate implementation of secondary school curriculum on students' academic performance in Dutsinma Local Government Area of Katsina State. This was observed as alluded to by the respondents in table 3 above. This findings agree with Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2010) stated that there should be the need to be a genuinely concern and specific activities to manage the change in curriculum implementation, tailored to the local context and the prevailing societal culture, as some societies are more eager to experiment and others are more conservative.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study. The findings concluded that the management were using the appropriate strategies/pedagogy for the adequate implementation of secondary school curriculum to lay solid foundations for the transiting students to tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government Area. It was evident and also discussed that there were so many factors militating against adequate implementation of the secondary school curriculum in Dutsinma Local Government area of Katsina State. These factors include inadequate qualified teachers, teaching aids and other facilitating materials, lack of laboratories and libraries and their facilities and so on affect effective implementation of secondary school curriculum and hence affects learning outcome of students transiting into tertiary institutions in Dutsinma Local Government area of Katsina State. The findings further concluded that these inadequacies in the curriculum implementation have resulted to increase in examination malpractice, mass failure in undergraduate courses of the first year students, resulting to low CGPA and finally lead to probation and subsequently advised to withdraw from the University.

Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Adequate and competent qualified teachers should be employed in both secondary and tertiary levels of education in Nigeria;
2. Training and retraining of teachers should always be carried out to handle the new innovations in the curriculum for smooth and adequate implementation;
3. Libraries and laboratories and their facilities always be made available;
4. Provision of the appropriate teaching aids for easy teaching and learning should be made available by the appropriate agents;
5. Teachers should always be motivated;
6. The facilities so provided should be monitored and managed appropriately; and
7. Appropriate teaching methods should always be used on each subject and topics to prepare students transiting to tertiary institutions.

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